

THE AFFECTED FARMS, THE ORGANIZATION OF WORK OF SPECIFIC PRINCIPLES AND FEATURES

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Annotatsiya. In this article, the farms that are necessary to the establishment of primary economic and legal knowledge which is beneficial from the aspect of the initial data and conclusions ketirilgan them.

Keywords: farm, agriculture, land, manufacturing, agricultural

To enter. Economic reforms carried out in the republic in the first years of independence, and the day today's agricultural industry in the economic process have been conducted to look into the work of agriculture, have gradual liberalization following the directions. Ie:

- the relations of production;
- land relations and land use;
- sales of agricultural products procurement systems;
- rural household goods, working out, including system and the regulation of lending rates;
- their distribution in agricultural products has been giving positive results.

The main part.

The market for the introduction of market relations in the agricultural sector and agricultural activities are suited to the principles of independence and freedom of the manufacturers of the goods at aspects of hugs, the main measures is being developed. This is directly specific to the formation of a healthy competitive environment and sustainable development in agriculture market to ensure it serves as an important factor.

The following basic processes in farm management , appears in the conditions (1-picture).

Achieved the independence of the republic of uzbekistan, the nation of the economy to market relations in order to conduct the necessary economic reforms were carried out, the formation of market economy in the republic achieved. The republic of socio - economic development of the lens conditions, taking into account the features in the implementation of economic reforms are paying great attention to agriculture. Along with this, see the farm in the country, with great attention paid to opportunities. Today, the number of farms and the number of them have been growing in the way wide open.

1-picture. The main processes of farm management[1]

Agriculture is one of the main sectors of the economic complex of the republic of the people:

- each of the development of many sectors of the economy agriculture the nation-provides you with different raw materials of the republic of the population

with food products. 75 percent of people used in the production of consumer goods, agricultural products;

- in agricultural production, irrigation and reclamation associated with irrigation systems. Agriculture irrigated land is taken from the product of 95 percent. Therefore, along with the problems of production in agriculture irrigation problems are also directly in the ground will find the solution at the desired level.

Agriculture increases the importance of the implementation of the features listed above. Consider the existing conditions in agriculture, the reforms are based on the following principles.

- rural economic reforms of state a clear goal directed connected with the implementation of agricultural policy; the preservation of the collective farms, adapted them to market relations

development of different resources to rebuild them and taking note of the form in form;

- agricultural management practices reject administrative and economic methods of management transition;

- to develop a wide range of farms and peasant farms, agricultural production land, property, labor to the results of the formation of a sense of ownership.

Based on this principle in the case of agricultural reforms in the republic to establish the legal base of agricultural enterprises and organizations of state tasarrufidan production, customization, peasant farmers and agriculture organization and development, tax and economy of agricultural pricing policy of building infrastructure agrobosor improvement, change management, improve the supply of material is being provided for the implementation of technical and other activities.

Ongoing analysis of economic reforms, their results confirmed that a thorough study of agricultural reforms will require further deepening of the time.

R-uzbekistanespublika the first president of 2003 24-march in "important trends in agricultural reforms deepening" a decree has been identified as a priority in the development of farmers. The future farming activities in the farm running the main form of agricultural remains. Class plays an important role in the formation of the farms of the village.

During the years of reforms in the country and the rest appeared to accumulate the many problems are solved on the basis of the decree of the president. Farms and dekhkan farms be given priority to the development of this first of all, the location of the plant the implementation of the work distribution of agricultural products produced, the results of labor and material resources to dispose of property that includes darashli him. From now on, expand the productive use of agricultural lands for the improvement of the relations of production rental form.

Farm production is much higher in comparison to the effectiveness of the company proved that. Mineral fertilizers in them, are used with fuel efficiency, material resources spent on average 2 times less per hectare.

His report to the president, "the farmer mean - this is primarily a man that has universal. Today with the words of a phrase to forty little too professional farmers of our nation", he noted.

At the same time also truly the peasants, too, agronomists, breeders also, the machine, also an accountant, economist and responsibility requires great knowledge in farming also. These requirements should be suitable to today's farmers.

Our farmers and peasant agriculture by the government for the development of the necessary legal, organizational and economic basis, they dramatically increase the number of product output and increase the volume of been created has been brought. Increasingly deepening reforms in agriculture, market economy in the conditions of functioning of the enterprises in the form of a competitive environment between the various property produces.

The Uzbek model of agricultural reforms in the country, on the basis of step-by-step are carried out. He and other peasant farmers in developing countries differs from the literal or cis give you the freedom to process their specific tdakllantirish healthy competition in the business market reforms, to strengthen the sense of ownership of property, goods producers farm to the village to teach the modern style of running.

As it is known, the initiative of the president created a new system of management and the guidance in agricultural sectors. On a number of areas hissadorlik associations independently organized and they started working. The activities of these entities are the most acceptable way to improve the living standards of people in the current stage of economic reforms, liberalization "process of implementation. The following represents the main aspects of his.

- price liberalization;
- the opportunity to create independent of the implementation of the economic activities of enterprises;
- eliminate obstacles to the development of the private sector;
- opertsiyalarni financial liberalization;

Agricultural enterprises in the conditions of market economy - an economic system in this complex dynamic, it is relatively independent of the organizational and operating umumishlab the production unit. Related to the national team and personal interests on the basis of her economic accounting is achieved.

Farms are independent economic entities, they all solve itself independently of economic and business affairs and implements, that is, the organization of production process and technology, the choice of the production system, the product is ready to sell the benefits of the use, is to offer a complex process performs financial operations management. In this process there are internal and external factors affecting the efficiency of farm management. Thus, external factors that affect the effective management of organizational resources-economic, socio-

political, international relations, technical-technological and market mechanisms, and we can add the contractual relationship. There are also internal factors that affect economic activity, if the financial resources, internal resources management system, level of qualification of the household head and the knowledge of its employees to work the attitude and the mechanics of risk management in agriculture into the organization of zm (2-picture).

2-picture. To the effective management of internal and external factors affecting farms[2]

The development of all processes in the universe as a system is available and will find it. Many of their number in a variety of ways, and the three - biological, natural, socio-economic system is to be. Socio-economic system and the role of farms in particular is worthy of note. Farm land rent in the material basis of production and private ownership of the production system consists of other tools. Another specific feature of this system – independent activities and freedom of business activity.

The farm of the internal system of technical and technological production, labor organization, the economic system is composed of. All system elements are mutually related to each other. The only economic system that are present in their joint effort in the way of shows. Each enterprise in a market economy, the organization of the activity in the open system view shows. In particular, the farm is no exception. Find the reason of the farms in the future development and operation based cooperative association (associations) for different services firms and market infrastructure provider it is difficult to imagine without. T affect the activities of the farm themashqi you can look at that system (3-picture).

3 -paint. Farm production activities of internal and external management systems[3]

But there are other systems that affect the activities of the farm. In particular, tax, environmental, demographic, and others. Denying this system without taking the cooperation in the research process, the author mainly aims to learn the activities of the service provider and market infrastructure.

Conclusion. The regulation and management of farm activities in the country of normative and legal basis for the creation and implementation is gradual. In particular, the economic and financial independence of the farms to ensure their rent given to the effective use of agricultural products, the production process of the formation of the system of the ministry of finance, to establish a system of training for farmers and agricultural enterprises (seed farms) on the basis of the establishment of farms and their management to improve economic relations between them on the basis of the construction of the improvement of market infrastructure, improvement of the system of financing the activities of the farm, type of product and to increase the quality of production choratadbirlar like to increase the practice are introduced. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added. The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.

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